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**Create an Enabling Environment for Bamboo Construction Sector in
Africa, Asia and Latin America**

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ABSTRACT

Bamboo has traditionally been used as a construction material for centuries. In the past two decades, innovation, technology development, deployment and demonstration, expanded the use of bamboo as a conventional construction material for both round bamboo and engineered bamboo structures. Bamboo is getting widely accepted and/or mainstreamed, and there has been increased attentions and uptake of bamboo as a contemporary construction material. This paper will showcase the lessons learnt from China, India, the Philippines, Nepal, Ethiopia, Uganda, Kenya, Ecuador, Colombia, Peru, etc., and provide a set of recommendations on how bamboo as a sustainable construction material can be mainstreamed to fill the gaps in sustainable construction as well as contributing to local jobs, income and economy.

KEYWORDS

Bamboo construction, sustainable management of bamboo forest, national strategy, capacity building, standardisation, carbon neutrality, round bamboo, engineered bamboo

BACKGROUND

Since the Industrial Revolution, the carbon dioxide and other green-house gases emitted by anthropogenic activities, such as burning fossil fuels, deforestation and agriculture expansion have contributed to the increased the average global surface temperature. Climate change is one of the greatest challenges for human-beings nowadays that requires urgent attention. During COP 26 in Glasgow, over 100 countries pledged to halt deforestation by 2030, which is critical to the overarching ambition of limiting temperature rises to 1.5 degrees Celsius (COP 26, 2021). In the context of ending global deforestation, bamboo is an alternative for timber, energy, fibre, food, feed and fodder in those countries with rich bamboo resources. As a construction material, bamboo can be alternated to replace several energy intensive products, such as concrete, steel, aluminum and plastics.

Bamboo is traditionally used as a construction material in more than 50 countries (Liu et al, 2019). Research and innovation in the past few decades have enabled bamboo's usage of a contemporary construction material in its original form as well as reconstituted forms. Globally, with rapid urbanization the quality as well as availability of the housing are a problem (UN-Habitat, 2020; UN-

Habitat et al, 2015). Meanwhile, the global building and construction sector which is one of the largest emitters of greenhouse gases, accounting for about 38% of emissions (IEA et al, 2019) is looking for low-carbon alternatives to achieve their carbon neutrality goals. As a widely available construction material in the global south with positive implications to GHG emission, bamboo holds tremendous potential as a green, locally available, affordable and resilient construction material in Africa, Asia and Latin America for housing supply.

CHARACTERISTICS OF BAMBOO AS A CONSTRUCTION MATERIAL

Locally availability

Bamboo is an important non-timber forest product around the tropical and sub-tropical regions of the world. It grows in an area of 35 million hectares across Asia, Africa and Latin America (FAO, 2020). In the global south, bamboo species suitable for round pole construction can be easily found in many countries and local people have traditional knowledge on bamboo housing and construction. Asia with the highest bamboo species diversity has about 20 bamboo commonly available and suitable bamboo species for construction (Liu et al, 2022c), while Americas and Africa have 8 and 5 species, respectively, see Table 1. In China, *Phyllostachys edulis* (moso bamboo) grows in an area of 4.68 million hectares and accounts for 73% of bamboo resources (Liu et al, 2022c), is the most commercialised bamboo species in the world and suitable for construction. In Africa, two indigenous bamboo species, *Oxytenanthera abyssinica* and *Oldeania alpina* are being widely used for construction. Moreover, naturalised species such as *Bambusa vulgaris*, *Dendrocalamus asper* and *Dendrocalamus giganteus* are also widely used. In Latin America, *Guadua angustifolia Kunth* is most common species used for construction and is very well known for its physical and mechanical properties. Colombia, Ecuador and Peru have more than 4.6 million hectares of bamboo forests, and *Guadua* is one of the predominant bamboo species (MINAGRICULTURA et al., 2020; MAG et al, 2018; SERFOR, 2022). Meanwhile, other species like *Dendrocalamus asper*, *Phyllostachys aurea*, *Otatea acuminata*, *Bambusa oldhamii* are also commonly used in Latin America (Ruiz-Sanchez, 2019).

Table 1. Common bamboo species for construction and their geographic distribution.

Region	Species
Asia-Pacific	<i>Bambusa balcooa</i> , <i>Bambusa bambos</i> , <i>Bambusa nutans</i> , <i>Bambusa pallida</i> , <i>Bambusa pervariabilis</i> , <i>Bambusa polymorpha</i> , <i>Bambusa tulda</i> , <i>Bambusa vulgaris</i> , <i>Bambusa blumeana</i> , <i>Dendrocalamus asper</i> , <i>Dendrocalamus giganteus</i> , <i>Dendrocalamus hamiltonii</i> , <i>Dendrocalamus strictus</i> , <i>Melocanna baccifera</i> , <i>Gigantochloa apus</i> , <i>Gigantochloa atrovioleacea</i> , <i>Gigantochloa atter</i> , <i>Gigantochloa macrostachya</i> , <i>Phyllostachys edulis</i>
Americas	<i>Guadua angustifolia</i> , <i>Guadua aculeate</i> , <i>Guadua amplexifolia</i> , <i>Dendrocalamus asper</i> , <i>Phyllostachys aurea</i> , <i>Otatea acuminata</i> , <i>Bambusa oldhamii</i> , <i>Bambusa vulgaris</i>
Africa	<i>Oldeania alpina</i> , <i>Oxytenanthera abyssinica</i> , <i>Bambusa vulgaris</i> , <i>Dendrocalamus asper</i> , <i>Dendrocalamus giganteus</i>

Physical and mechanical properties

Bamboo has naturally optimized structural form (straight hollow tube with diaphragms at nodal regions) that makes them suitable for construction. It's lightweight with high strength and stiffness along the fibres adds to its robustness and resistance against natural disasters, such as earthquakes and tropical storms (Janssen, 2000; Salzer, 2018). For round bamboos, its material properties are generally proportional to its density and normally higher than those of softwood (Liu et al, 2022c). Properties of engineered bamboo are not greatly different than those of their source bamboo, but with much less variation in tested properties than round bamboo (Liu et al, 2022b). Bamboo's strength weight ratio is much higher than concrete and very close to steel (Janssen, 2000). In order to make full use of its high compression and tension properties along fibres, appropriate structural forms can be implemented for bamboo structures, such as arches, trusses, bamboo-steel hybrid structures etc.

Properties of carbon storage

Like timber, bamboo forests can absorb carbon dioxide through photosynthesis. In the context of global climate change, bamboo can greatly help carbon storage both as plant and as durable products. If bamboo products are used to construct houses, carbon could be sequestered for decades or even longer. Studies of total ecosystem carbon on certain woody bamboo species can store 94 to 392 tons of carbon per hectare (Lugt et al., 2018). Unlike trees, bamboo can be selectively harvested annually (20-30%) of biomass without replanting (Jayaraman and Long, 2020). Studies on carbon sequestration, storage in durable products and avoided carbon emission by replacing energy intensive materials can sequester and/or store carbon comparable to the fastest growing species in the world (Lou et al, 2010; Lugt et al., 2018).

CREATING AN ENABLING ENVIRONMENT TO PROMOTE BAMBOO AS A CONSTRUCTION MATERIAL

To mainstream bamboo as a construction material, several interventions are necessary and based on its development and lessons learnt from different projects as well as countries, the following sections discuss the enabling environment considering key elements such as: 1) Set up sustainable management of bamboo forests for raw material supply; 2) Develop international and national standards on bamboo construction; 3) Develop national regulation and incentives to promote the use of bamboo; 4) Increase scientific research on bamboo construction; 5) Promote capacity building of skilled workers and professionals; 6) Scale up demonstrated bamboo construction projects; 7) Promote information exchanges and strength international cooperation.

Set up sustainable management of bamboo forests for raw material supply

As a biomaterial, bamboo is produced by natural forests or grown in farms. Therefore, its natural quality (especially the species, age of bamboo, season of harvesting etc.) is very important for utilising it directly in original or reconstituted forms. Setting up sustainable management systems of bamboo forests and farms, such as sustainable plantation, selection of bamboo culms, choose suitable harvest seasons, preservation and drying, as well as grading of bamboo culms can guarantee sufficient quantity and consistent quality of the raw material supply.

- 1) **Sustainable plantation:** Like crops, bamboo's biological characteristics or properties is determined based on species, agro-climate, spacing/density, and management practice (Wang et al., 2019). Fig 1. shows the comparison between managed and unmanaged bamboo forests for monopodial and sympodial bamboo in China and Ecuador, respectively. Culms from unmanaged forests are apparently slim with smaller diameter which are not meet the requirements of being as construction materials. Moreover, the quality – physical and mechanical properties of the bamboo will be diverse and affect the quality of construction. Sustainable plantation not only improves the quality of raw material, but also increase its yield thereby increasing incomes of local farmers. A well-managed plantation yields 20-30 tons (air-dry) of bamboo per ha per year (Janssen, 2000). Meanwhile, a managed bamboo forests results in greater removal of greenhouse gases compared to unmanaged stands, promoting its potential to help mitigate climate change (Lou et al, 2010; Kuehl et al, 2013).
- 2) **Selection of bamboo culms:** Choosing right species is critical, due to the diameter, wall thickness, taper are critical variables for construction which determines the properties. Importantly, harvesting bamboo with right age is also critical as it influences the mechanical properties and the durability of poles, referring to Table 1 or depending on the experience of local people for selecting right species. For age selection, 3-5 years old bamboo culms are commonly recommended to be harvested (Correal et al, 2010; Jayaraman and Long, 2020). Unmatured bamboo culms below 3 years old have low lignification which could not provide required strength and stiffness for construction purposes. For sustainable management of forests, accessibility both in terms of road/infrastructure and regulations for harvesting is critical. In China, growing industrialised bamboo sector required large amount of raw bamboo materials, where the government enabled the construction of forest roads and forest use/access permits that aided in availability of required quality and quantity of raw materials.
- 3) **Suitable harvest seasons:** it is recommended to harvest bamboo for construction purposes in winter or non-rain seasons due to with lower-starch and -moisture content (Janssen, 2000). High starch content makes bamboo culms be easier to be mildewed and higher moisture contributes to higher shrinkages, cracking and fungal growth. However, as round culm storage system has not been

established due to limited industry scale, therefore it is difficult to avoid to harvest bamboo in summer or autumn. According to the interview of round bamboo and engineered bamboo manufacturers in China, India, Ecuador and Ethiopia, further treatment is the most important aspect to ensure durability of bamboo structures, and the treatment cost is slightly higher for bamboo's harvested during off-seasons.

(a) Unmanaged Moso bamboo forest for around 10 years in China.

(b) Managed Moso bamboo forest in China.

(c) Unmanaged Guadua bamboo forest in Ecuador

(d) Managed Guadua bamboo forest in Ecuador.

Figure 1: Comparison of managed and unmanaged bamboo stands. (Credit: Fig. 1a, 1b by Ding Yulong; Fig. 1c, 1d by Fabian Moreno)

- 4) **Preservation and drying:** Natural bamboos are susceptible to insects and fungal attack. Preservation by either non-pressure or pressure methods using fixing chemicals can greatly improve its durability of bamboo as a structural material. Soaking bamboo in preservative solution (dip diffusion) enables the preservative to penetrate bamboo culms in natural rate by capillary action are the main non-pressure methods (NMBA, 2006). Pressure methods can force the preservative to penetrate into the bamboo, which is more effective but require pressure vessels or facilities that are more expensive to establish (INBAR, 2001; Liese et al., 2003). Bamboo is a hygroscopic material that adsorbs moisture in variable quantities depending on the relative humidity of the place and the surrounding atmosphere temperature. The moisture in some cases can reach 80% to 150% (Montoya and Gutierrez, 2021). However, for structural bamboo components, the recommended moisture is around 12% (ISO, 2021). Several drying techniques have been developed considering natural and artificial processes, in which natural air-dry bamboo is the most recommended method to avoid split.
- 5) **Grading of bamboo culms:** bamboo culms suitable for construction need to meet relevant requirements for its thickness, diameter, taper, etc. (ISO, 2019). There are several steps and criterions for raw material suppliers to categorise bamboo into construction purpose. Firstly, bamboo culms with minimum defects and good relation between diameter and wall thickness could classify as structural grade. Those poles are normally selected for structural components such as columns or beams (However, smaller diameter species less than 50 mm or bamboos that cannot fit the quality standards for structures can also be used for the wall slats, purlins and decoration purposes, which is not included for the discussion in the section). Secondly, the grading not only will provide better

quality material for the final users, but also it will improve the value chain by benefiting the producers and allow them to offer more products. The grading process can reduce the percentage of waste in the bamboo production. 20%-30% bamboo waste could be used as bioenergy for boilers in the factories of raw material suppliers.

Based on INBAR's project experience and interviews of local experts and entrepreneurs in different countries, Table 2 shows the status of the establishment of sustainable management of bamboo forests for raw material supply to commercialise the construction sector in different countries.

Table 2. Establishment of sustainable management of bamboo forests for raw material supply to commercialised construction sector in different countries.

Region	Country	Sustainable plantation	Selection of bamboo culms	Suitable harvest seasons	Preservation and drying	Grading of bamboo culms
Africa	Ethiopia	√	√	×	√ (Limited)	×
	Kenya	√	√	×	×	×
	Uganda	×	√	×	√	√
Asia	China	√	√	×	√	√
	India	√	√	×	√	√
	The Philippines	√	√	×	√	√
	Nepal	×	√	×	√	×
	Indonesia	×	√	×	√	×
Latin America	Colombia	√	√	×	√	√
	Ecuador	√	√	×	√	√
	Peru	√	√	×	√	√

Develop international and national standards on bamboo construction

For structural uses of bamboo, the development of national standards is critical for local people to use them in buildings, due to legal status and national regulations for building's safety. Standards are very critical for promotion of bamboo in its use as a construction material. Review of literature indicate that (see Appendix A), 17 countries developed their national standards related to bamboo construction, including Brazil, China, Colombia, Ecuador, Ethiopia, India, Indonesia, Italy, Kenya, Nepal, the Netherlands, Peru, the Philippines, United Kingdom, United States of America and Vietnam. Around half of them, noted with an asterisk (*) in Appendix A, adopt ISO standards published by International Organization for Standardization (ISO) as their national standards directly, that is the most efficient way to be recommended to countries who are interested in bamboo construction. As ISO standards are intended to guide all the countries across the world, it normally provides the basic principles and methods, and there is no specific data for certain bamboo species yet. When countries adopt or use ISO standards for real projects, they need to collect and analyse data of their local bamboo species.

INBAR works with ISO since 2000, and convenes global experts to develop and refine international standards for both round bamboo and engineered bamboo structures (Liu et al, 2019). Table 3 shows all the published ISO standards and standards under development as well their current status by ISO TC165 WG 12 (Working Group 12 on structural uses of bamboo within the Timber Committee). As ISO 22156:2004, ISO 22157-1:2004 and ISO 22157-2:2004 have been withdrawn and are superseded by updated versions, those countries who are still using the old ones should update on time.

Some countries developed their own national standards based on ISO standards and established a large database for the application of certain bamboo species. For example, the Colombian national standard for *Guadua* bamboo structures NSR-10, Title E and G is the result of the work of local researchers in Colombia, they have established and maintained a large database for the application of *Guadua* bamboo in building construction since 2002 when the first standard was published, the NSR-98, Title E for one and two story bahareque houses, and greatly supplement appropriate regional data to ISO standards as well. In addition, these standards were considered as reference for the development of the Technical Normative E.100 Bambú for Peru in 2012 and National Ecuadorian Code (NEC) – *Guadua* Structure GaK in 2015. Currently, they are the only three countries in the American continent who have national

standards on bamboo. Additionally, Mexico and Brazil have been working on their own standards during the last five years.

Table 3. ISO TC165 standards for bamboo construction (Liu et al, 2022c)

Designation	Standard	Status
ISO 22156:2004	<i>Bamboo — Structural design</i>	replaced by ISO 22156:2021
ISO 22157-1:2004	<i>Bamboo — Determination of physical and mechanical properties — Part 1: Requirements</i>	replaced by ISO 22157:2019
ISO/TR 22157-2:2004	<i>Bamboo — Determination of physical and mechanical properties — Part 2: Laboratory manual</i>	withdrawn
ISO 19624:2018	<i>Bamboo structures — Grading of bamboo culm — Basic principles and properties</i>	active
ISO 22157:2019	<i>Bamboo Structures — Determination of physical and mechanical properties of bamboo culms — Test methods</i>	active
ISO 22156:2021	<i>Bamboo Structures — Bamboo culms — Structural design</i>	active
DIS 23478	<i>Bamboo structures — Engineered bamboo products — Test methods for determination of physical and mechanical properties</i>	TC 165 Draft International Standard
CD 5257	<i>Bamboo Structures - Engineered bamboo products - Test methods for determination of physical and mechanical properties at small scale</i>	TC 165 Committee draft
NWIP 7567	<i>Bamboo Structures — Glued laminated bamboo — Product specification</i>	TC 165 New Working Item Proposal
Technical Specification	<i>Bamboo structures — Engineered bamboo products — Design of engineered bamboo structures</i>	approved for development by TC 165

Develop national strategies and incentives to promote the use of bamboo

Although bamboo is an important non-timber product in the global south, the national strategies, policies, regulations for promotion of bamboo and development of bamboo sector is largely lacking in many bamboo growing countries. In the recent years, about ten countries have issued their national policies, strategies or action plan to promote the development of bamboo sector (see Table 4). As an international intergovernmental organization, INBAR facilitated and participated the development of national policies of most of the countries listed in Table 4. Meanwhile, INBAR has also helped Ethiopia, Ghana and Cameroon develop their policy integration analysis (Minale and Abebe, 2020; Nfonkrah et al, 2020; Oduro et al, 2020), which helped the establishment of Ethiopia’s national strategy and will promote the release of other countries’ national policies in the near future.

National policies and strategies are intended to formalize and organise the bamboo sector and boost the market. All the national policies and /or strategies and action plan highlight the uses of bamboo as construction and structural materials for houses, bridges, fences etc. In China, its latest national policy clearly indicates that China will enhance the utilisation of bamboo construction materials to contribute its carbon neutrality goals in 2060. Additionally, China also carried out its national consulting project “Research on Development Strategies and Key Technologies for the Bamboo Construction Sector in China towards 2035”, funded by Chinese Academy of Engineering. The national research project aimed to assess the use of bamboo construction, and provided a series of suggestions to the Chinese government how to expand the sector (Yang and Liu, 2021; Jiang et al, 2021).

In Latin America, some countries also released incentives to promote the uses of bamboo in the construction sector. In Ecuador, with the supports of INBAR and the Spanish Agency for International Development Cooperation (AECID), local governments who are in charge of the approval of new building construction and the collection of the annual property tax released financial incentives on

bamboo construction. In 2019 and 2021, the municipalities of Santa Ana, El Carmen and Portoviejo in Manabí province enacted a municipal regulation that provide a reduction up to 70% annual property tax payment if the new structure is built with a minimum of 75% of bamboo. In Peru, Piura Province (especially the municipalities of Lalaquiz, San Juan de Bigote and Yamango) recognized bamboo as a safe building material in disaster prone zones and its contribution to climate change mitigation and adaptation.

Table 4. Issued national policies related to boost bamboo construction sector in different countries.

Country	Issue time	National policies / Strategy / Programmes	Leading Ministry
China	2021	Opinions on Accelerating the Innovative Development of Bamboo Industry	National Forestry and Grassland Administration of the People's Republic of China
Colombia	2020	Competitiveness Agreement of the <i>Guadua</i> / Bamboo Productive Chain and its Agroindustry. 2020 – 2030	Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development
Ecuador	2018	Ecuador: National strategy of bamboo (2018-2022)	Ministry of Agriculture and Animal Husbandry
Ethiopia	2020	2019-2030 Ethiopian Bamboo Development Strategy and Action Plan	Ethiopian Environment, Forest and Climate Change Commission (EFCCC)
India	2019	Operational Guidelines of National Bamboo Mission	Ministry of Agriculture and Farmers Welfare of India
Madagascar	2018	Madagascar Bamboo Industry Development Policy and National Strategy	Ministry of Environment, Ecology and Forestry of Madagascar
Peru	2022	National Bamboo Strategy for Peru 2022-2025	Ministry of Agriculture / The National Forestry and Wildlife Service (SERFOR)
Rwanda	2011	National Bamboo Policy	Ministry of Forestry and Mines of the Republic of Rwanda
The Philippines	2021	New policy on the establishment, harvesting, and transport of bamboo	The Philippine Council for Agriculture, Aquatic and Natural Resources Research and Development of the Department of Science and Technology (DOST-PCAARRD)
Uganda	2020	2019-2029 Uganda National Bamboo Strategy and Action Plan	Ministry of Water and Environment of Uganda

Increase scientific research on bamboo construction

Basic and applied research on bamboo as a construction material is critical for the further development of the sector. Fig. 2 and Fig. 3 shows the funding agencies and research institutions by the bibliometric analysis for published English peer-reviewed articles on bamboo construction via the Web of Science Collection Core (WSCC) (Liu et al, 2022c). Except for the UK Research Innovation, Engineering Physical Sciences Research Council (UK) and the National Science Foundation (US), other seven funding agencies are mainly from China, including both national and provincial agencies (see Fig. 2). Not surprisingly, 14 out of top 24 research institutions published the most articles published on bamboo construction showed in Fig. 3 are from China. Other institutions from USA (2), UK (3), India (1), Colombia (2), German (1) and Brazil (1) also contributed to the research on bamboo construction.

Despite great advances in modern bamboo architecture, the scientific research of bamboo construction materials still lags far behind other construction materials, such as concrete, steel and timber. From the perspective of research content, further investigations should be carried out as follows: 1) Database on

the physical and mechanical properties for all common and widely distributed bamboo species suitable for construction and its reconstituted materials should be established, as lack of data inhibits wide usage and large-scale industrialization; 2) Current research mainly focus on the mechanical properties of the materials, however, people’s concerns on its durability and fire-resistant performances are real reasons restricting the large-scale application of bamboo structures in the market; 3) Currently, bamboo structures are normally built in small-span and under three-storey buildings. However, bamboo’s excellent mechanical properties of high tensile and compression strength have not fully utilised. Research on innovative cross laminated bamboo materials as well as bamboo-steel-concrete hybrid structures, which can expand the variety of scenarios of using bamboo in large-span and high-rise buildings; 4) At present, the cost of engineered bamboo materials is not competitive with that of engineered timber materials. Innovative manufacturing process can improve the material utilization of raw bamboo culms and its production efficiency. Therefore, relevant research on manufacturing equipment and processes are critical; 5) other researches on joints for round bamboo structures and structural glue for engineered bamboo are also need further exploration.

Figure 2. Funding agencies identified in WSCC search. (Liu et al, 2022c)

Figure 3. English language papers from WSCC search. (Liu et al, 2022c)

Promote capacity building of professionals and skilled workers on bamboo construction

Strengthen the capacity building of professionals, such as designers, architects, engineers, and skilled workers is critical to establish a healthy and sustainable value chain for promoting bamboo construction sector. However, the mechanism and means of training different professionals are different.

- 1) For university students: there are two ways for university students to learn bamboo as a construction material. One is through short-term courses, which have been set up by some universities in different countries, including the UK, China, Indonesia, Colombia and Ecuador etc. Another one is by bamboo-themed competitions. In recent years, bamboo-themed competitions related to architecture or landscape architecture become new ways of “Learn by doing” to expose university students to the study of bamboo as a construction material (Liu et al, 2022a). A series of competitions led or supported by INBAR have trained more than 10,000 university students around the world in recent five years (Liu et al, 2022b; Liu et al, 2022c) (see Fig. 4).
- 2) For skilled workers on bamboo: like timber, on-site construction of bamboo building needs local technicians, such as carpentries to cut bamboo, make joints et al. Since its establishment, INBAR has been trained thousands of local skilled workers on bamboo construction in different countries, such as Nepal, Bhutan, Ethiopia, Kenya, Uganda, Ecuador, Colombia, Peru etc. Last year, the Workshop School for Sustainable Bamboo Construction implemented in Ecuador by INBAR with the support of AECID, designing a non-formal education program for local young people. During 2021, 74 students participated the workshop school and obtained a certificate of labor competency on bamboo construction after completing 560 hours theory courses and 250 hours on-site practices (Fig. 5).

Scale up demonstrated bamboo construction projects

As indicted before, more than 50 countries use bamboo as a construction material. However, the uptake of bamboo in mainstream construction market is still limited. Experience on scaling up demonstrated social housing projects in Ecuador and the Philippines worth sharing with other countries. In Ecuador,

several bamboo housing prototypes had been approved by the Ministry of Urban Development and Housing, which were included in their national housing plan (MIDUVI, 2019). For example, after the earthquake in provinces of Manabi and Esmeraldas in 2016, several private and public bamboo housing projects were implemented. Till 2019, 2842 temporary (Fig. 6a) and permanent bamboo houses (Fig. 6b) were built for 17 communities in these two provinces (Proyecto META, 2020). In 2020, the government program “House for All” was implemented by the Ministry of Housing of Ecuador. 27 bamboo houses (66 m² each) and three community structures (300 m² each) were constructed as demonstration units. In 2021, the National Plan for Habitat and Housing towards 2025 made the plan to build at least 31,000 houses by using local materials, for which bamboo is considered as a main material (MIDUVI, 2021).

Figure 4. 2019 International Bamboo Construction Competition. (Credit: INBAR)

Figure 5. Workshop School for Sustainable Bamboo Construction in Ecuador. (Credit: Fabian Moreno)

(a) Temporary bamboo house in Ecuador

(b) Permanent bamboo house in Ecuador

Figure 6: Scale up bamboo houses built in Ecuador. (Credit: Fig. 6a by Miguel Camino; Fig. 6b by the Ministry of Urban Development and Housing of Ecuador)

In the Philippines, Base Bahay Foundation (Base) has built around 1000 permanent bamboo houses (Fig. 7a) in the whole archipelago since 2014. Base uses a construction system called Cement Bamboo Frame technology inspired by the bahareque technology from Colombia but with the structural modification to withstand typhoons. The houses have an average area of 28 m² and the walls are prefabricated. Base Bahay plans to build 10,000 home in the province of Negros Occidental, the Philippines together with Habitat for Humanity (HFH). Additionally, Base has started a project in Nepal in collaboration with HFH Nepal, where 100 permanent houses (Fig. 7b) of 50 m² were built in 2021 and 500 structures will be built in 2022 and 2023.

Promote information exchanges and international cooperation

Bamboo’s utilisation as a construction material has been practiced and applied across the world, including the countries rich in bamboo resources, new emerging countries with bamboo industry development goals, as well as developed countries with no bamboo resource base but have advanced technologies that aim to develop and use low-carbon materials. Due to large gaps of information sharing among countries, regions as well as international societies, there is an obvious unbalanced development

of the bamboo construction sector across different countries. To move the sector forward, information exchanges and international cooperation in this aspect need to be further promoted.

(a) Permanent bamboo house in the Philippines

(b) Permanent bamboo house in Nepal

Figure 7: Scale up bamboo houses built in the Philippines and Nepal. (Credit: Base Bahay Foundation)

On one hand, as described in the above sections, it is very significant to strengthen the information exchange on cultivation technologies for ensuring high-quality bamboo raw materials; technologies for value addition; the international and national standardization, national regulations and incentives; as well as the best practices of bamboo construction projects. Information exchange and sufficient communications among all stakeholders from countries and regions should be highly enhanced, including policy makers, experts and private sectors through workshops, trainings, seminars, etc.

On the other hand, an extensive, in-depth and efficient international cooperation on scientific, technical, financial and policy aspects is to be expected by the joint actions of seminars, summits, dialogues, negotiations, etc. A number of INBAR Member States have published their National Bamboo Strategies so far, the experience of which can be shared with other countries. Colombia, Ecuador and Peru set up very good examples. They established national roundtables on bamboo sector with the support of INBAR since 2013. As national strategic forums, bamboo roundtables have had a leading participation in the process of local normative design and policy advocacy, providing consultancy to all the aspects of bamboo sector and well-delivering the latest information from international societies.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The paper mainly focuses on the seven key elements to discuss how to create enabling environment to mainstream bamboo as a construction material in Asia, Africa and America. The conclusion as well as a series of recommendations are provided as follows:

- 1) High-quality raw materials in sufficient quantity is critical for the development of the bamboo construction sector. Follow the required procedure described in the article, countries can guarantee the sustainable supply of raw bamboo culms. Support the development of infrastructure, and establish preservation and treatment facilities can greatly improve the supply chain.
- 2) National standardisation on bamboo construction can help recognise bamboo as an acceptable construction material to compete with other construction material in all the countries. Encourage more countries to use existing international standards as the basis to develop their own national standards.
- 3) National regulations, and a series of financial and non-financial incentives can greatly promote bamboo to be used as a construction material. In the context of climate change, low carbon bamboo materials can be considered to be included in the carbon trading system in the future.
- 4) Increase funding for the scientific research on bamboo construction can generate empirical data and innovative methods for using bamboo as a structural material, improving its competitiveness with other mainstreamed materials in the market.
- 5) Promote capacity building of skilled workers and professionals have been carried out in different countries by setting up short-term courses, organising competitions and trainings. Develop a pool

- of professions by workshop schools while developing relative curriculums on bamboo construction in formal and non-formal education to train more engineers, architects and craftsmen.
- 6) Scale up demonstrated bamboo construction projects to improve public awareness is important to ameliorate the poor perception of bamboo as a non-durable construction material. Develop iconic large-span and high-rising bamboo structures to improve public confidence on it.
 - 7) Promote information exchanges and strength international cooperation on bamboo construction related research, technology, standards, regulation as well as incentives to support the development of the sector across different countries.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

All necessary data is presented in this paper.

REFERENCE

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Appendix A. Published national standards on bamboo construction in different countries

Country	Designation	Standard	Language
Brazil	ABNT NBR 16828-1 (2020)	<i>Estruturas de bambu Parte 1: projeto</i>	Portuguese
	ABNT NBR 16828-2 (2020)	<i>Estruturas de bambu Parte 2: Determinação das 12ecánicas12s físicas e 12ecánicas do bambu</i>	

China	GB/T 15780-1995	<i>Testing methods for physical and mechanical properties of bamboos</i>	Chinese
	GB/T 37805-2019	<i>Bamboo winding composite pipe</i>	
	GB/T 38071-2019	<i>Structural laminated bamboo sliver curtain lumber</i>	
	GB/T 40487-2021	<i>Structural bamboo glulam</i>	
Colombia	NTC 5407: 2018	<i>Structural joints with Guadua angustifolia Kunth</i>	Spanish
	NTC 6338: 2019	<i>Coffers with Guadua angustifolia Kunth</i>	
	NTC 6413: 2020	<i>Bamboo structures. Grading of bamboo culms. Basic principles and procedures</i>	
	NTC 5525: 2021	<i>Bamboo structures. Determination of physical and mechanical properties of bamboo culms. Test methods</i>	
Ecuador*	GPE INEN 20 (1987)	<i>Practice guide. Scaffolding. Round wood and bamboo</i>	Spanish
	NTE INEN-ISO 22156 (2017)	<i>Bamboo structure design (ISO 22156:2004, IDT)</i>	
	NTE INEN-ISO 22157-1 (2017)	<i>Bamboo. Determination of physical and mechanical properties Part 1: Requirements (ISO 22157-1:2004, IDT)</i>	
	NTE INEN-ISO 22157-2 (2017)	<i>Bamboo. Determination of physical and mechanical properties Part 2: Laboratory Manual (ISO/TR 22157-2:2004, IDT)</i>	
Ethiopia	ES 6416: 2021	<i>Design of bamboo structures</i>	English
	ES 6417: 2021	<i>Preservation of bamboo for construction purpose</i>	
India	SP 7: 2016	<i>National building code of India 2016, section 3 Timber and bamboo: 3B</i>	English
	IS 16096: 2013 (2018)	<i>Bamboo - Jute composite hollow core door shutter - Specification</i>	
	IS 16073: 2013 (2018)	<i>Bamboo - Jute composite panel door shutter - Specification</i>	
	IS 15912: 2018	<i>Structural design using bamboo - Code of practice</i>	
	IS 6874: 2008 (2019)	<i>Method of tests for bamboo</i>	
	IS 10145: 1982 (2020)	<i>Bamboo supports for camouflaging equipment</i>	
	IS 7344: 1974 (2020)	<i>Bamboo tent poles</i>	
	IS 8242: 1976 (2020)	<i>Methods of tests for split bamboos</i>	
Indonesia*	SNI ISO 19624:2018 (2021)	<i>Bamboo structures – Grading of bamboo culms – Basic principles and procedures</i>	English
	SNI ISO 22157:2019 (2021)	<i>Bamboo structures – Determination of physical and mechanical properties of bamboo culms – Test methods</i>	
Italy*	UNI 11842:2021	<i>Bamboo – Determination of physical and mechanical properties of bamboo culms</i>	Italy
Kenya*	KS: ISO 22156: 2004	<i>Bamboo structural design</i>	English
	KS ISO 19624: 2018	<i>Bamboo structures – Grading of bamboo culms – Basic principles and procedures</i>	
	KS ISO 22157: 2019	<i>Bamboo structure – Determination of physical and Mechanical properties of bamboo culms – Test Methods</i>	
	KS 2856: 2019	<i>Preservation of bamboo for structural purposes – Code of practice</i>	
Nepal	NBC 204: 1994	<i>Guidelines for earthquake resistant building construction: earthen building (EB) (part 3 materials 3.4 bamboo; part 9 9.3 bamboo for flooring and roofing; part 10 seismic – resistant components)</i>	English

Peru	E. 100 (2012)	<i>Technical standard: E. 100 bamboos</i>	Spanish
The Netherlands *	NEN-ISO 19624:2018	<i>Bamboo structures – Grading of bamboo culms – Basic principles and procedures</i>	English
	NEN-ISO 22157:2019	<i>Bamboo structures – Determination of physical and mechanical properties of bamboo culms – Test methods</i>	
	NEN-ISO 22156:2021	<i>Bamboo structures – Bamboo culms – Structural design</i>	
The Philippines*	PNS ISO 19624:2020	<i>Bamboo structures – Grading of bamboo culms – Basic principles and procedures</i>	English
	PNS ISO 22157:2020	<i>Bamboo structures – Determination of physical and mechanical properties of bamboo culms – Test methods</i>	
	PNS ISO 22156:2021	<i>Bamboo structures – Bamboo culms – Structural design</i>	
Uganda	US 2114:2020	<i>Preservation of bamboo and cane for structural purposes -Code of practice</i>	English
United Kingdom*	BS ISO 19624:2018	<i>Bamboo structures. Grading of bamboo culms. Basic principles and procedures</i>	English
	BS ISO 22156:2021	<i>Bamboo structures. Bamboo culms. Structural design</i>	
	BS ISO 22157:2019	<i>Bamboo structures. Determination of physical and mechanical properties of bamboo culms. Test methods</i>	
United States of America**	ASTM D5456 – 21e1	<i>Standard specification for evaluation of structural composite lumber products</i>	English
Vietnam*	TCVN 8168-1:2009	<i>Bamboo. Determination of physical and mechanical properties. Part 1: Requirements</i>	Vietnamese
	TCVN 8573:2010	<i>Bamboo. Structural design</i>	
	TCVN 8168-2:2010	<i>Bamboo. Determination of physical and mechanical properties. Part 2: Laboratory manual</i>	

* Countries who adopt ISO standards as their national standards.

** ASTM standards are voluntary consensus standards used by individuals, companies and institutions around the world.